

MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND OPTICAL ROTATORY POWERS OF *p*-HYDROXY- α -NAPHTHYLIMINOCAMPHOR.

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The magnetic susceptibility and rotatory powers of *p*-hydroxy- α -naphthyliminocamphor have been described. The two forms of the compound have different susceptibilities which suggest that the differences are not due to the size of the aggregate of the molecules or stereoisomerism, but probably due to the difference in the constitutions.

Aryl derivatives of iminocamphor (Forster and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 944; Singh and collaborators, *ibid.*, 1919, 115, 566; 1920, 117, 980; 1599) with a few exceptions exist in one form only, though Singh and Rai (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 389) have pointed out that these compounds by virtue of their containing an azethenoid group are capable of existing in two stereoisomeric forms. Singh and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 76S) have prepared *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylaminophenyliminocamphors, which are phototropic and the two forms show different rotatory powers. It is supposed that the substances exist in stereoisomeric forms.

p-Hydroxy- α -naphthyliminocamphor exists in two forms (red and light orange). The red form, prepared by crystallising from alcohol, is converted into the light orange form at 132-135°. This thermotropic change may be due to one of these causes; (i) a change in the size of the aggregate of the molecule, (ii) or to geometrical isomeric change as suggested by Singh and Singh (*loc. cit.*), and (iii) constitutional change.

To decide this we have determined the magnetic susceptibilities of the two forms on a modified form of a Guoy's balance. The values are: -6.58×10^{-7} for the red and -6.46×10^{-7} for the light orange.

Bhatnagar, Kapur and Hashmi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 573) as the result of their study of the magnetic susceptibilities of phototropic compounds have come to the conclusion that the susceptibility value of the compound before and after exposure to light would remain the same if the phototropic change is not accompanied by any change in the crystal structure or a change in the constitution.

Again Bhatnagar, Mathur and Neogi (*Z. Physik.*, 1930, 69, 373) have shown that the difference in the magnetic susceptibilities of the geometrical isomerides is negligible being of the order 0.032×10^{-7} to 0.052×10^{-7} . The susceptibility values of the two forms of *p*-hydroxy- α -naphthyl-

iminocamphor, however, differ by 0.120×10^{-7} , showing thereby that the thermotropic change from red to light orange is neither due to the change in the size of the aggregate of the molecule nor to the geometrical isomerism. If the constitution of the two varieties be represented by the following formulae, then the net change in the mass susceptibility value of the compounds due to the various constitutional changes works out to be 0.121×10^{-7} , which agrees remarkably well with the experimental value.

Both the forms were examined polarimetrically in various solvents. The light orange form shows mutarotation in aniline, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol. The final value of the light orange form is the same as that of the red form and it appears that this is the rotatory power of the equilibrium mixture. There is no mutarotation in ethyl alcohol if 2-3 drops of pyridine are added and it seems that the equilibrium is established within a very short time. The rotatory powers of both the forms in nitrobenzene are almost identical and the light orange form shows no mutarotation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Camphorquinone and 1:4-Aminonaphthol Hydrochloride.

—Equimolecular quantities of camphorquinone and 1:4-aminonaphthol hydrochloride with fused sodium acetate were heated on a water-bath at $45\text{--}50^\circ$ for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was then extracted with alcohol and precipitated with water and the process repeated several times till the product was bright orange in colour free from tarry matter. The precipitate was crystallised from warm alcohol as bright red crystals, melting at 231° but with a change to light orange colour at $132\text{--}135^\circ$. It crystallised from hot alcohol as deep red crystals with blackish tinge. On spontaneous crystallisation both the varieties separated side by side and were mechanically separable.

At a slightly higher temperature ($50\text{--}65^\circ$) the yield decreases considerably, most of it changing to a black product and finally at a temperature of 80° , the whole product reduces to a black tarry matter. (Found: N, 4.86. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 4.56 per cent).

1 : 4-Aminonaphthol was prepared in good yield by reducing benzene-azonaphthol with sodium hydrosulphite ("Organic Syntheses" Vol. III). Attempts to prepare it by the reduction of *p*-sulphobenzene-azonaphthol with stannous chloride (Barnett, Preparation of Organic Compounds, 191) yielded resinous tarry matter.

The rotatory powers were determined in the usual way in a 2-dm tube with the exception of aniline in the case of red form where 1 dcm tube was used.

Red form

Solvents	Conc. g/25 c.c.	α_D	$[\alpha]_D$
Aniline	0.0212	1'20°	1415°
EtOH	0.0100	1'08	1350
Me ₂ CO	0.0114	1'22	1337
MeOH	0.0100	0'98	1225
Nitrobenzene	0.013	1'19	1144

Light Orange form

Aniline	0.0140	1'80	1608
(after 21 hours)		1'62	1434
EtOH	0.0142	1'63	1435
(after 9 hours)		1'46	1285
EtOH	0.0100	1'05	1312
In the presence of 2-3 drops of pyridine			
MeOH	0.106	1'16	1368
(after 24 hours)		1'04	1226.4
Nitrobenzene	0.0100	0'95	1187

The rotatory powers of *p*-hydroxy-phenyliminocamphor were determined in the following solvents for the sake of comparison.

Aniline	0.0202	2'75°	1701°
Nitrobenzene	0.0217	2'43	1393